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MEASUREMENT OF MOISTURE DIFFUSION COEFFICIENT OF WOOD USING TERAHERTZ WAVE

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Introduction

➤ Effect of Moisture content variation in wood

- Swelling or shrinkage occurs as the moisture content in the wood changes.
- These phenomenon cause distortion, which varies depending on the grain direction of the wood.
- Therefore, it is necessary to study analysis of hygroscopicity according to grain direction, and measurement of moisture content in wood.

Experimental method

- **Two absorption test**

1. Immersion experiment

- Measurement of weight change for calculation of diffusion coefficient according to absorption time

2. Contact absorption

- Conduct Terahertz imaging for analysis of moisture diffusion process and diffusion coefficient

- **Terahertz time domain spectroscopy (THz-TDS)**

- THz radiation lies in the region of the electromagnetic spectrum between 100 GHz to 30 THz which overlaps from the upper frequency range of microwaves through the far infrared.

- THz radiation has an extreme sensitivity to moisture contents since it easily absorbed by moisture in THz region.

- THz signals were examined while drying the moisture absorbed balsa wood in order to figure out the relationship between the THz intensity and moisture content.

Results and discussion

• Terahertz Images

- Through THz images, the absorption area could be identified. It was observed that absorption was rapidly occurred at the initial step.
- Using THz images, 3D moisture concentration gradient image could be obtained. Through these images, the degree of local moisture absorption could be identified.

Method	Weight change		THz technique	
	Long.	Tang.	Long.	Tang.
Diffusion coefficient ($10^{-8} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$)	10.94	3.58	11.23	3.43

• Diffusion coefficient

- Using the 3D moisture concentration gradient image and Fick's law, the diffusion coefficient was calculated. It was found that the diffusion coefficient was different by grain direction, due to the difference of diffusion mechanism.
- The diffusion coefficient of THz method were similar with that of weight change method.
- Improving the solution procedures, THz measurement would be a useful technique for measurement of moisture content and diffusion coefficient.